

Introductory Text:

This study aims to investigate how AI tools are used in Requirements processes. Your participation will help to establish new knowledge and guidelines for future engineers and developers in the field of Requirements engineering. The research is conducted by researchers from CERIS (Centre for Empirical Research on information systems) at Örebro University, Sweden.

The results may be published in academic venues, i.e., journals or conferences. However, the individual responses will never be disclosed.

Your responses will be kept strictly confidential. Data will be stored securely and analyzed in a way that ensures your privacy. This survey is completely anonymous. No personally identifiable information will be collected, and your responses cannot be traced back to you. All data will be analyzed in aggregate form only. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without any consequences.

If you have questions or queries, please contact Dr. Panagiota Chatzipetrou, Associate Professor (Panagiota.chatzipetrou@oru.se) or Dr. Muhammad Hanif, Associate Assistant Professor (muhammad.hanif@oru.se), both belonging at Department of Informatics, Örebro University, Sweden.

Demographics:

Q1

1. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

Q2

2. How old are you?

- Under 27 years
- 28-37 years
- 38-47 years
- Over 47 years

Q3

3. What is your role in your company?

- Business Analyst / Requirements Engineer
- Architect
- Tester
- Developer
- Product Manager
- Data scientist / AI specialist
- Project Manager
- Other (Please specify)

Q4

4. What is your highest level of education?

- High school Graduate
- Bachelor Degree
- Master Degree
- Doctorate Degree

Q5

5. How many years of relevant work experience do you have? (Number of years after completing education)?

- 0-2 years
- 2-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- More than 15 years
- Prefer not to answer

Q6

6. What is the size of the company?

- Small (1-50 employees)
- Medium (51-500 employees)
- Large (501+ employees)

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Q7

7. How familiar are you with AI technologies in the context of software development?

- Not familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Familiar
- Very familiar

Q8

8. What AI Techniques you use in your projects when dealing with Requirements?

- Natural Language Processing (NLP) for analyzing requirements
- Machine Learning (ML) for predictive requirement discovery
- Cognitive computing for understanding stakeholder needs
- Knowledge representation for requirements modeling
- Other

Q9

9. What are the directions of using AI in requirements engineering in your organization?

- Emerging trends, such as autonomous systems engineering
- The role of Explainable AI (XAI) in requirements understanding
- Integration with other technologies (e.g., blockchain, IoT)
- Other, please specify

Q10

10. Does using AI tools reduce the time or effort required for RE tasks?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Moderate
- Mostly
- Very

Q11

Which AI tools are you using in RE tasks?

Q12

11. How are requirements elicited in your organization?

- Group interaction techniques
- Individual participation techniques
- Reading based techniques
- Market research
- Reuse
- Experiment
- External consultancy
- Don't know

Q13

12. How do you use AI tools in elicitation process in your organization?

- Gathering feedback and ideas
- Generating surveys
- Lists of interview question
- Collaborative brainstorming partner
- Summarize the key points
- The AI tools can accelerate the finalization process, know also as "culmination"

Q14

13. What challenges do you face when using AI in elicitation in your organization?

- Challenges related to AI Understanding Context
- Challenges related to AI perpetuate Bias in Data
- Challenges related to stakeholder's Trust and Adoption
- Challenges related to Ethical Concerns
- Challenges related to Integration Complexity
- No challenge
- Other

Q15

14. How accurate is the requirement elicitation with the use of AI?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Moderate
- Mostly
- Very

Q16

15. How accurate is the requirement analysis with the use of AI?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Moderate
- Mostly
- Very

Q17

16. How satisfied are your customers with AI-generated requirements?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Moderate
- Mostly
- Very

Q18

17. How scalable are AI-driven RE tools?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Moderate
- Mostly
- Very

Q19

18. How adaptable are AI-driven RE tools?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Moderate
- Mostly
- Very

Q20

19. What are the benefits in using AI in Requirements Elicitation?

- Please specify

Q21

20. Would you recommend the use of AI in requirements elicitation to other teams?

- Definitely
- Probably
- Not sure
- Probably not
- Definitely not

Q22

21. Which quality attributes would be prioritized to be elicited with AI? Imagine you have \$100 to allocate to prioritize the quality attributes to be elicited with AI. How would you distribute the money among the following quality attributes? (Please allocate exactly \$100)

	Value Allocation
Functional [e.g., completeness and correctness]	<input type="text"/>
Maintainability [e.g., reusability and testability]	<input type="text"/>
Usability [e.g., learnability and user interface aesthetics]	<input type="text"/>
Performance efficiency [e.g., time behavior and resource utilization]	<input type="text"/>
Portability [e.g., adaptability and replaceability]	<input type="text"/>
Compatibility [e.g., co-existence and replaceability]	<input type="text"/>
Security [e.g., confidentiality and authenticity]	<input type="text"/>
Reliability [e.g., availability and fault tolerance]	<input type="text"/>
Other	<input type="text"/>

Q23

22. How long is the typical time needed to elicit a quality for your product? (traditional methods)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

Q24

23. How long is the typical time needed to elicit a quality for your product? (using AI)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

Q25

24. How are Requirements specified? (artifact used)

- NL sentences
- Textual artifacts: Use cases, user stories
- Graphical elements: Mockups, diagrams, tables
- General models: UML meta models, Domain models
- Others

Q26

25. What templates and guidelines, if any, are followed to specify requirements?

- Organization
- Methodology
- Tools
- Standard
- Document layout
- Requirments attributes
- How to write guidelines
- Quality assurance
- Other

Q27

26. What classification schemes, if any, are used for organizing requirement specifications?

- Main functionalities
- Characteristic
- Part of the systems
- Other

Q28

27. What classification tools, if any, are used for organizing requirement specifications?

- MS office
- Modeling
- Project management
- Big systems
- Other

Q29

28. What are the different types of challenges occur in requirement specification phases of the projects?

- Requirement management
- Generation of documents
- Versioning
- Communication
- Traceability
- Verification and validation
- Other

Q30

29. How are AI tools used in the Specification process?

- generating requirement documents from natural language descriptions
- choosing the AI tool/model for this RE phase - being pre-trained on the INCOSE Guidelines for Writing Requirements, which helps detect and prevent a number of quality issues
- Extraction - finding domain-typical terms in requirements, eg to create glossaries
- Classification - categorizing requirements according to predefined types, eg functional and non-functional
- Modeling - representing requirements as models in various forms
- ChatGPT can tackle creating such visual process artifacts as flow or swimlane diagrams and data schemas
- Conversion to other languages (including both use cases such as eg English -> Chinese and business domain languages Non-Gherkin -> Gherkin)
- Other

Q31

30. Which phase of software development do you think benefits the most from AI integration?

- Requirements specification
- Design
- Implementation
- Testing
- Maintenance

Q32

31. What challenges have you faced when using AI for requirements specification?

- Lack of understanding
- High cost
- Integration issues
- Data privacy issues
- No significant challenges
- Other

Q33

32. Would you recommend the use of AI in requirements specification to other teams?

- Definitely
- Probably
- Not sure
- Probably not
- Definitely not

Q34

33. Which quality attributes would be prioritized to be specified with AI? Imagine you have \$100 to allocate to prioritize the quality attributes to be specified with AI. How would you distribute the money among the following quality attributes? (Please allocate exactly \$100.)

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Compatibility [e.g., co-existence and replaceability]	<input type="text"/>
Security [e.g., confidentiality and authenticity]	<input type="text"/>
Reliability [e.g., availability and fault tolerance]	<input type="text"/>
Other	<input type="text"/>

Q35

34. How long is the typical time needed to specify a quality for your product? (typical methods)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

Q36

35. How long is the typical time needed to specify a quality for your product? (using AI)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

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Q37

36. How important is explainability in AI-driven requirements analysis for your projects?

- Extremely important
- Very important
- Moderatly important
- Slightly important
- Not important at all

Q38

37. What is the major advantage of using AI in requirements analysis?

- Improved accuracy
- Faster processing
- Cost reduction
- Enhanced collaboration
- Better documentation

Q39

38. How are AI tools used in the Analysis process?

The AI models can provide recommendations to:

- Clarify ambiguities
- Uncover implicit needs
- Identify inconsistencies, conflicts, or missing information against predefined criteria

Comment

Q40

39. How much time does your team typically spend analyzing the quality of your product? (typical methods)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

Q41

40. How long does it typically take to analyze the quality of your product? (using AI)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

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Q42

41. What are the challenges in using AI in Validation?

Q43

42. How are AI tools used in the Validation process?

- Functional proofs of concept (or minimum viable products), not just design prototypes. That allows users to quickly test multiple variations, analyze their performance, and identify elements to improve in the next requirement cycle
- Can be implemented in production to monitor, detect, and categorize errors since manual root cause analysis can significantly increase the workload
- Other

Q44

43. Which quality attributes would be prioritized to be validated with AI? Imagine you have \$100 to allocate to prioritize the quality attributes to be validated with AI. How would you distribute the money among the following quality attributes? (Please allocate exactly \$100)

	Value Allocation
Functional [e.g., completeness and correctness]	<input type="text"/>
Maintainability [e.g., reusability and testability]	<input type="text"/>
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Compatibility [e.g., co-existence and replaceability]	<input type="text"/>
Security [e.g., confidentiality and authenticity]	<input type="text"/>
Reliability [e.g., availability and fault tolerance]	<input type="text"/>
Other	<input type="text"/>

Q45

44. How long does your team typically spend validating the quality of your product? (Typical methods)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

Q46

45. "How long does it typically take to validate the quality of your product? (Using AI)

- Less than 1 hour
- Less than 8 hours
- Less than 1 week
- Less than 1 month
- Other

Q47

46. How often do you use AI tools for requirements management in your projects?

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

Q48

47. How do you rate the accuracy of AI-generated requirements compared to traditional methods?

- Much more accurate
- More accurate
- About the same
- Less accurate
- Much less accurate

Q49

48. What is your primary source of information for learning about AI in requirements engineering?

- Academic journals
- Industry conferences
- Online courses
- Professional networks
- Company training

Q50

Do you have any additional comments or suggestions regarding the use of AI in software component selection and evaluation?